

Application of some Hydroxamic Acids for Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium(II)

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A sensitive and selective method for extraction spectrophotometric determination of Pd^{II} as a binary complex with *N-m*-chlorophenyl-*p*-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid (*m*-CMBHA), extracted from aqueous phase at pH 3.0 and ternary complex of PAN in isoamyl alcohol has been described. The binary and ternary complexes have the molar absorptivities 4.7×10^4 (λ_{max} 400 nm) and 1.2×10^4 (λ_{max} 620 nm) dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹, respectively. Palladium was determined in the standard samples.

PALLADIUM is used as a catalyst for hydrogenation and dehydrogenation in liquid and gas phase reactions, most important use of palladium is in low current electrical contacts. There are several organic reagents used for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of palladium¹⁻⁶. However, they are less sensitive, time consuming, tedious and several metal ions, viz. Pt^{IV}, Ir^{III}, Ru^{III}, Rh^{III} etc. interfere⁷⁻¹⁴. Hydroxamic acids are potential analytical reagents and have been reported for the estimation of various metal ions¹⁵⁻¹⁹. No data are available for the extraction and a spectrophotometric determination of palladium, except *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHA) and *N-p*-chlorophenylbenzohydroxamic acid^{20,21}. In the present investigation, *N-m*-chlorophenyl-*p*-substituted-benzohydroxamic acids are studied for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of palladium. *N-m*-Chlorophenyl-*p*-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid is found to be the most sensitive reagent amongst the hydroxamic acids and hence, the detailed studies are reported. The present system is comparable in sensitivity and its selectivity with commonly used reagents, like dithiazone and that its selectivity can be increased by the use of suitable marking agents.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR and G.R. grades, unless otherwise specified. Hydroxamic acids used for the extraction were synthesised as described elsewhere²², and were recrystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) before use. The purity of the hydroxamic acids were checked by m.p. uv and ir spectra. A 0.1% (w/v) solution of the reagent was prepared in isoamyl alcohol for extraction purposes.

A 0.1% (w/v) solution of 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN) in 95% ethanol was prepared for ternary complex study. A standard palladium solution was prepared by dissolving a requisite amount of palladium chloride (Johnson Matthey) in 0.1 M HCl; its final concentration was determined gravimetrically²³.

The spectral measurements were made on a VSU 2-P spectrophotometer with 1.0 cm quartz cells. The pH measurements were made with a Systronics digital pH meter.

Procedure: An aliquot of Pd^{II} solution (85.32 μ g) was taken in a 60 ml separatory funnel, and the pH adjusted to 3.0 with 0.1 M HCl and 0.1 M NH₄OH. A 0.1% (w/v) solution (10 ml) of reagent in the isoamyl alcohol was then added and shaken for 15 min, the phases allowed to separate and the organic phase was transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask after drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The extraction was repeated with the reagent solution (2 \times 2.5 ml) and the extract collected to the mark with isoamyl alcohol and the absorbance measured at 400 nm against the blank.

For the ternary complex, 0.1% (w/v) PAN in 95% ethanol (2 ml) was added into the binary complex extract and diluted to 25 ml with isoamyl alcohol. The absorbance of the green coloured complex was measured after 20 min at 620 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The spectral characteristics of binary complexes of the palladium with the *N*-arylhydroxamic acids are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTIC OF PALLADIUM-HYDROXAMIC ACID COMPLEXES

Hydroxamic acids	Absorbance	λ_{max} nm	molar absorptivity $\times 10^3$ $dm^2 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$
<i>N-m</i> -Chlorophenylbenzo	0.120	420	3.7
<i>N-m</i> -Chlorophenyl- <i>p</i> -Tolylbenzo	0.125	400	3.9
<i>N-m</i> -Chlorophenyl- <i>p</i> -Methoxybenzo	0.150	400	4.7
<i>N-m</i> -Chlorophenyl- <i>p</i> -Chlorobenzo	0.100	410	3.1
<i>N-m</i> -Chlorophenyl- <i>p</i> -Bromobenzo	0.100	410	3.1
<i>N-m</i> -Chlorophenyl- <i>p</i> -Fluorobenzo	0.100	410	3.1

To enhance the sensitivity of the method PAN was added as a chromogenic reagent. The green ternary complex has absorbance maximum at 620 nm. The spectral characteristics of the ternary systems are given in Table 2. Among the hydroxamic acids used here *N-m*-chlorophenyl-*p*-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid (*m*-CMBHA) was found to be the most sensitive reagent for palladium.

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTIC OF PALLADIUM-HYDROXAMIC ACID-PAN COMPLEXES

Hydroxamic acids	Absorbance	Colour	Molar absorptivity $\times 10^4$ $dm^2 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$
<i>N-m</i> -Chlorophenylbenzo	0.320	Green	1.0
<i>N-m</i> -Chlorophenyl- <i>p</i> -Tolylbenzo	0.350	Green	1.1
<i>N-m</i> -Chlorophenyl- <i>p</i> -Methoxybenzo	0.390	Green	1.2
<i>N-m</i> -Chlorophenyl- <i>p</i> -Chlorobenzo	0.288	Green	0.9
<i>N-m</i> -Chlorophenyl- <i>p</i> -Bromobenzo	0.288	Green	0.9
<i>N-m</i> -Chlorophenyl- <i>p</i> -Fluorobenzo	0.288	Green	0.9

Effect of pH: A set of experiment was carried out in order to study the influence of pH on extraction of Pd with *m*-CMBHA complex. The final pH of each aqueous solution was measured before extraction. The results (Table 3) show that the maximum extraction (100%) is obtained at the pH range 2.8-3.4; below and above this the extraction decreases and hence, the optimum pH 3.0 is selected for the present investigation.

Effect of reagent concentration: The extraction of Pd²⁺ (85.32 μ g/25 ml) was carried out with varying amounts of 0.1% (w/v) *N-m*-chlorophenyl-

 TABLE 3—EFFECT OF pH ON EXTRACTION OF PALLADIUM WITH *N-m*-CHLOROPHENYL-*p*-METHOXYBENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID (*m*-CMBHA)

pH	Extraction %	Pd- <i>m</i> -CMBHA $\lambda_{max} = 400$ nm		Pd- <i>m</i> -CMBHA-PAN $\lambda_{max} = 620$ nm	
		Colour	Molar absorptivity $dm^2 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$	Colour	Molar absorptivity $dm^2 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$
1.0	3	LY	1.4×10^3	Y	3.6×10^2
2.0	15	LY	7.0×10^3	Y	1.1×10^3
2.5	64	Y	3.0×10^3	GY	7.7×10^3
2.8	100	Y	4.7×10^3	G	1.2×10^4
3.0	100	Y	4.7×10^3	G	1.2×10^4
3.2	100	Y	4.7×10^3	G	1.2×10^4
3.4	100	Y	4.7×10^3	G	1.2×10^4
4.0	8	LY	3.7×10^3	Y	9.6×10^3
5.0	3	LY	1.4×10^3	Y	3.6×10^3

LY \equiv Light yellow. Y \equiv Yellow. GY \equiv Greenish yellow. G \equiv Green.

p-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid in isoamyl alcohol. It was observed that 10 ml of 0.1% (v/v) *m*-CMBHA was quite sufficient for the quantitative extraction of palladium. Excess of the reagent can be used without any difficulty.

Effect of PAN concentration: Various chromogenic reagents, viz. PAR, brilliant green, crystal violet, xylenol orange, 1,10-phenanthroline, PAN, arsenazo III were tried for ternary complexes and for increasing the sensitivity of the method. PAN was found to be the most suitable for the spectrophotometric determination (Table 4).

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF PAN CONCENTRATION

Sl. no.	0.1% PAN ml	Absorbance	Colour	Molar absorptivity $\times 10^4$ $dm^2 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$
1.	0.5	0.350	Green	1.1
2.	1.0	0.390	Green	1.2
3.	2.0	0.390	Green	1.2
4.	3.0	0.390	Green	1.2
5.	4.0	0.370	Green	1.1

For maximum colour development 2 ml of 0.1% (w/v) PAN (in 95% ethanol) was enough. Lower concentration of the reagent gave incomplete complexation while the large excess increased the blank intensity.

Extraction time and stability of complex: Optimum time for the extraction was found to be 15 min though higher shaking time did not have any adverse effect on the extraction. The binary and ternary complexes are stable for 24 and 12 h, respectively.

Validity of Beer's law: The yellow binary complex of Pd^{II}-*N-m*-chlorophenyl-*p*-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid has maximum absorbance at 400 nm with a molar absorptivity $4.7 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Pd-*N-m*-chlorophenyl-*p*-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid-PAN ternary complex has maximum absorbance at 620 nm having molar absorptivity $1.2 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The binary and ternary systems obey Beer's law in the range 12-130 and 0.5-130 ppm, respectively.

Effect of diverse ions: In order to examine the utility of this method in the presence of other ions, their interference were studied Table 5. Pd is extracted in presence of diverse ions with *m*-CMBHA and then the colour developed by PAN. The several ions associated with palladium do not interfere. Fe^{III}, Ti^{IV}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and V^V are interfere in the determination of Pd. However, the interferences of Fe^{III} and V^V, Ti^{IV} and Co^{II} and Ni^{II} are eliminated by masking with ascorbic acid, fluoride and 1,10-phenanthroline, respectively.

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS

Palladium = 3.4 ppm		$\lambda_{max} = 620 \text{ nm}$	
Reagent = 0.1% (10 ml)		Path length = 1 cm	
Solvent = Isoamyl alcohol		pH = 3.0	
PAN = 0.1% (2 ml) in Ethanol		Absorbance = 0.390	
Ions	Added as	Amount mg	Absorbance
Mg ^{II}	MgSO ₄	60	0.390
Be ^{II}	Be(NO ₃) ₂	40	0.390
Ba ^{II}	BaCl ₂	60	0.391
Pb ^{II}	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	60	0.389
Cu ^{II}	CuCl ₂	40	0.389
Bi ^{III}	Bi(NO ₃) ₃	30	0.391
Mo ^{VI}	Na ₂ MoO ₄	50	0.391
Ca ^{II}	CaCl ₂	40	0.390
Hg ^{II}	Hg(NO ₃) ₂	50	0.390
U ^{VI}	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	40	0.389
Ti ^{IV} ^a	TiOCl ₂	30	0.391
Fe ^{III} ^b	FeCl ₃	40	0.391
Ni ^{II} ^c	NiSO ₄	40	0.390
V ^V ^a	NH ₄ VO ₃	60	0.391
Co ^{II} ^c	CoCl ₂	60	0.390

Masked with : ^afluoride, ^bascorbic acid, ^c1,10-phenanthroline.

Analysis of palladium in standard samples: A weighed quantity of the catalyst sample (Fluka) was digested with a mixture of perchloric and nitric acids and centrifuged. The filtrate was concentrated by heating and diluted to 100 ml with 0.05 M HCl. An aliquot of this solution was used for extraction

of Pd. The method proposed has been applied to the determination of palladium in Pd/CaCo₃ catalyst and in other samples (Table 6). Results obtained are in agreement with those quoted.

TABLE 6—DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM IN HYDROGENATION CATALYSTS

Catalyst	Standard value %	Palladium found, %	
		AAS	Present method*
Pd/Charcoal	5	4.93	4.98
Pd/Asbestos	5	4.98	5.01
Pd/BaSO ₄	10	9.98	9.97
Pd/Charcoal	10	10.01	9.98
Pd/Carbonate	6	5.99	6.01

*Average of five values

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References

1. F. E. BEAMISH and W. A. E. MCBRYDE, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1953, 9, 349
2. O. MENIS and T. C. RAINS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1955, 27, 1932.
3. M. OYOMO, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1980, 116, 161.
4. W. D. JACOBS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1961, 33, 2179.
5. K. L. CHENG, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, 26, 1844.
6. R. B. SINGH, B. S. GARG and R. P. SINGH, *Talanta*, 1979, 26, 425.
7. V. K. GUSTIN and T. R. SWEET, *Anal. Chem.*, 1963, 35, 44.
8. M. IZQUIERDO, Thesis, Universidad Autonoma-Barcelona, 1982.
9. E. R. MARHENKE and E. B. SANDELL, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1963, 28, 259.
10. R. S. YOUNG, *Analyst*, 1951, 76, 49.
11. O. MENIS and T. C. RAINS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1955, 27, 1932.
12. K. L. CHENG and B. L. GOYDISH, *Microchem. J.*, 1966, 10, 158.
13. Z. MARCZENKO and M. JAROSZ, *Talanta*, 1981, 28, 561.
14. V. M. IVANOV, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1967, 22, 763.
15. Y. K. AGRAWAL, *Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 1980, 5, 3.
16. Y. K. AGRAWAL and S. A. PAIEL, *Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 1980, 4, 230.
17. Y. K. AGRAWAL and R. K. JAIN, *Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 1982, 6, 50.
18. R. PANDE and S. G. TANDON, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 990.
19. M. I. SHTOKAL, M. I. OSTROVSKAYA, V. L. RYZHENKO and V. N. TOLOK, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1978, 33, 2383.
20. A. D. SHENDRIKAR, *Talanta*, 1969, 16, 51.
21. Y. K. AGRAWAL and S. P. CHUDASAMA, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1981, 90, 1033.
22. Y. K. AGRAWAL and S. G. TANDON, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1977, 16, 371, 495.
23. A. I. VOGEL, "Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis Including Elementary Instrumental Analysis", 4th. ed., E.L.B.S., London, 1978, p. 474.